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Standardising Data Management Plans for Machine-Actionable Data Management across NFDI and beyond

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Abstract

Achieving FAIRness of research data requires the application of best practices and machine-actionable metadata. Data management plans (DMPs) as a starting point for research data management activities can support both, when implemented as machine-actionable DMPs (maDMP) [1]. Machine-actionable DMP templates and tools adapted for community-specific needs communicate best practices and standardised workflows, provide up-to-date information on service offers, and connect all stakeholders involved in the RDM process. In order to achieve this interconnection, a standard for DMP templates is needed that consortia and services can rely upon.

The NFDI basic service in development DMP4NFDI works towards this goal by developing a NFDI-wide standard for DMPs, the *NFDI DMP Template Framework*, and providing a common tool connecting consortia and their RDM services: RDMO. DMP4NFDI is based on the work of the cross-consortia working group *infra-dmp* in NFDI section Common Infrastructures, and the vision developed in its workshops and discussions [2].

Our standard development is based on two core principles: 1) ensuring interoperability across NFDI consortia as a prerequisite for metadata exchange and cross-consortia solutions, 2) allowing community-specific adaptations when needed. As a starting point, the de facto standard for maDMPs developed and maintained by the RDA “DMP Common Standards” working group [1] was chosen, as it ensures international interoperability. This standard is already supported by RDMO, the DMP tool most used in Germany. We derive a cross-consortia standard for DMP templates by thoroughly mapping questions currently used in DMP templates. Through feedback loops and workshops, we ensure cross-consortia agreement. By involving the broader RDM community in the discussion, we are paving the way for adaptation beyond NFDI.

Based on the standard it is possible to exchange information between DMPs and services offered by the consortia. Standardised answer options can be used to offer information on community-specific services in the moment a need arises, to book or prepare data services for research projects, or to connect researchers with data management experts. DMP4NFDI supports consortia in developing community-specific DMP solutions for their communities,

integrating services with RDMO, and offering general DMP support and training. The service development is supported by several NFDI consortia which have provided requirements, general feedback, and have adopted the service to offer DMP support within their respective communities.

Keywords: Data Management Plan, machine-actionable, Standard, Basic Service

Resources

- Research Data Management Organiser (RDMO): <https://rdmorganiser.github.io> "DMP tool provided by DMP4NFDI"
- DMP4NFDI Website: <https://dmp.services.base4nfdi.de/> "Information on DMP4NFDI service"

Author contributions

SS: Conceptualization; Writing – review & editing

KD: Conceptualization; Writing – review & editing

MGO: Conceptualization; Writing – review & editing

DW: Software;

JW: Conceptualization; Writing - original draft;

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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References

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